

MICROMECHANICAL MODELING OF CERAMICS-BASED COMPOSITES VIA VORONOI-DELAUNAY NETWORKS

Khalid I. Alzebdeh¹, Uwe B. Kruger²

¹Department of Mechanical and Industrial Engineering, Sultan Qaboos University
P.O. Box 33, Al-Khod, PC 123, Sultane of Oman
Email: alzebdeh@squ.edu.om

²Department of Biomedical Engineering, School of Engineering, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute,
Jonsson Engineering Center, Troy, NY USA 12180-3590
Email: krugeu@rpi.edu

Keywords: Ceramics, Voronoi, Delaunay, Elastic moduli, Statistical Planar Element

ABSTRACT

This article examines the mechanical behavior of a 2D class of random media using a discrete modeling approach. To capture physical randomness, the paper utilizes the Voronoi tessellation to simulate a random microstructure of a two-phase ceramics-based composite. Given the duality of the Delaunay triangulation to the Voronoi tessellation, the presented work studies the effect of randomness in this microstructure upon the effective elastic moduli. Interactions between neighboring grains are modeled via the Delaunay network in which each vertex represents a grain and each edge is a two-force member acting as a linear spring. More precisely, we consider finite “windows of observations” as a statistical planar element (SPE). A proper displacement-controlled (essential) boundary condition applied to the SPE generates approximate uniform strain field in the models, which corresponds to calculating one elastic modulus at a time. Then, the effective Young’s modulus and Poisson’s ratio of the continuum are extracted from the calculated elastic moduli. Conducting a number of Monte Carlo simulations for different parameter setups allows estimating the first and second order characteristic of the random fields of effective elastic moduli. The results obtained support the usefulness of this framework for developing analytical models of various random heterogeneous solids.

1 INTRODUCTION

Advanced ceramics-based composites are a class of materials which exhibit superior properties compared to traditional ceramics. Generally, they are treated as a two-phase microstructure composed of particles including a primary (hard) phase that is embedded into a secondary (soft) matrix phase. Ceramics are widely used as a tool material for high speed machines which are made from metallic materials. They are well established in a number of industries, including the automotive and aerospace industries [1].

The microstructure plays an important role in determining the mechanical behavior of ceramic composite materials. Associated properties may consequently be affected by microstructure parameters, for example the grain size, the shape of the grain and the distribution of constituent phases [2]. It is, therefore, difficult to quantify the correlation between the microstructure and the materials properties given the high complexity of the microstructure.

Recently, several numerical and theoretical studies have been conducted to quantify this correlation. Carolan *et al.* [3,4] showed that strength and toughness of ceramic composites are highly

affected by both, the size of the primary phase and the percentage of the matrix phase. Teng *et al.* [5] examined the effect of the particle size upon the mechanical properties of alumina-based ceramics.

In fact, the research community has extensively studied and evaluated the effect of adding a secondary phase into the microstructure upon the mechanical properties of ceramics. Cai *et al.* [6] examined the effect of adding TiC into Al₂O₃ based composites. Lui *et al.* [7] investigated the effect of starting powders size on Al₂O₃/TiC composites. Commonly, Al₂O₃-based ceramics tool materials were strengthened by the addition of micro-sized particles, for example TiC, TiN ZrO₂, (WTi)C, TiB₂, to improve their mechanical properties [8].

Representation of various heterogeneous solids, e.g. granular media, in terms of planar simple finite graphs have been implemented [9,10]. These implementations rely on the dual graphs Delaunay network and Voronoi tessellation to model random media and are applicable over a wide range of different applications. While the Voronoi tessellation is predominantly employed to generate geometrical models for complex microstructures, Delaunay networks allow modeling the interaction between neighboring grains.

For applications to ceramic and metallic materials, in both 2D and 3D, Nygards and Gudmundson [11] used Voronoi tessellation to create 3D geometrical models of two-phase ferrite/pearlite steel with periodic boundary conditions. Zhou *et al.* [12] considered a Voronoi tessellation to investigate the crack propagation in ceramics tool materials. Most recently, a combined experimental-numerical method was used to investigate the role of the microstructure upon the fracture of advanced ceramics [13]. Based on a similar approach, Dong *et al.* [14] investigated the flexural behavior of ceramic tool materials.

Despite the reported work in the literature, the research community has not paid significant attention to examine the effect of randomness in the distribution of micro-structural parameters for polycrystalline materials. The objective of this article is to develop a micro-level model for simulating the elastic mechanical properties of a class of ceramic composites. The model was based on the dual Delaunay-Voronoi tessellation in which a random algorithm was employed to take into account the primary phase volume fraction, the microscale particle size and the grain distribution of one (stiff) phase into the second (soft) matrix phase.

2 DELAUNAY NETWORK MODEL

The random microstructure model is generated by placing a finite number of random points that follow a Poisson distribution in a region of an \mathbb{R}^2 plane. Next, the nearest neighbors for a given Poisson point generate a Voronoi polygon (Poisson-Voronoi tessellation). Then, the Poisson points and their nearest-neighbor connections are called a Poisson-Delaunay network. Each Voronoi cell is occupied by a grain and the topology of all grain-grain interactions is represented by a Delaunay graph network. Fig.1 exemplifies a dual Delaunay network-Voronoi tessellation with 100 seed points.

In the Delaunay graph, bonds represent normal (central) interaction between neighboring grains which are modeled by linear elastic springs that have a constant k^n . Shear interactions are modeled by angular springs with a constant k^a . The actual assignment of k^n and k^a depends on the specification of a particular grain, that is of the soft (secondary) or the stiff (primary) phase. Their respective volume fractions in this two-phase network are V_s and V_p , respectively. Halving each vertex then allows constructing the individual grains that are either soft or stiff with specified spring constant k^n and k^a . Furthermore, the stiffness of any half-length, $l = s/2$, for a given edge is given by, k_i^n / l where $i = 1$ or 2 . Here, s is the Euclidean distance between two points and $i = 1$ or 2 describes the hard or soft phase, respectively. Finally, the angular spring constants k^a are assigned depending on whether they belong to the soft- or the type-hard grain.

Figure 1: (a) A Delaunay network with 100 vertices; (b) Dual Voronoi tessellation; and (c) both overlaid to show duality.

3 A TWO-PHASE RANDOM CERMAICS MODEL

Consider a random, planar, ceramics medium, whose micro structural connectivity is modeled by a Delaunay planar graph. In a statistical sense, the random medium B is defined as:

$$B = \{B(\omega); \omega \in \Omega\} \quad (1)$$

and is a family of deterministic specimens $B(\omega)$, where ω is a realization from the sample space Ω [15]. For simplicity, we consider $B(\omega)$ to be a 2D SPE for the random composite ceramics where the randomness is in the distribution of the primary phase into the secondary phase. Mechanical properties of the random composite B say the bulk modulus κ is treated as:

$$\langle \kappa \rangle = \int_{\Omega} \kappa(\omega) p(\omega) d\omega \quad (2)$$

where $p(\omega)$ is the probability density function of κ and $\langle \cdot \rangle$ is the ensemble average over the sample space Ω . Based on these stochastic concepts of random field theory and on the discrete Delaunay model of microstructure, any mechanical property of a random composite can be defined. With this in mind, the locally isotropic constitutive law can be stated as follows:

$$\sigma_{ij} = \kappa(\omega, \delta) \delta_{ij} \varepsilon_{kk} + 2\mu(\omega, \delta) \varepsilon_{ij} \quad (3)$$

where κ and μ (shear modulus) are characterized by a random distribution over the body sample domain and are function of δ , with δ being a dimensionless ratio:

$$\delta = \frac{L}{d} \quad (4)$$

in which L is the length of the square SPE and d is the average grain diameter. Depending on the specified boundary conditions, the problem results in solving the partial differential equation:

$$\sigma_{ij,j} = 0 \quad (5)$$

If the moduli on the micro scale vary its solution will provide, consequently, some locally averaged information. Furthermore, seeking an overall constitutive equation of the body at the macroscale level gives rise to:

$$\sigma_{ij} = \kappa^{eff} \delta_{ij} \varepsilon_{kk} + 2\mu^{eff} \varepsilon_{ij} \quad (6)$$

where κ^{eff} , μ^{eff} are the effective Lamé constants at the macroscopic level which are defined based on the ensemble averaging over the body's sample space of specimens (realizations). Moreover, a particular specimen $B(\omega)$ is subjected to the following displacement boundary condition:

$$u_i = \varepsilon_{ij}^0 x_j \quad (7)$$

Where ε_{ij}^0 is a uniform strain field over the domain of $B(\omega)$. For this boundary value problem, the solution of $\sigma(\mathbf{x})$ and $\varepsilon(\mathbf{x})$ for the point \mathbf{x} belongs to the realization currently analyzed. Then, the effective constitutive law can be defined as:

$$\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle = \langle \kappa \rangle \delta_{ij} \langle \varepsilon_{kk} \rangle + 2\langle \mu \rangle \langle \varepsilon_{ij} \rangle \quad (8)$$

Furthermore, the application of the ergodicity condition leads to an ensemble averaging for the mean energy density:

$$\langle U \rangle = \frac{V}{2} [\langle \kappa \rangle \varepsilon_{ij}^0 \varepsilon_{jj}^0 + 2\langle \mu \rangle (\varepsilon_{ij}^0 \varepsilon_{ij}^0 - \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_{ii}^0 \varepsilon_{jj}^0)] \quad (9)$$

from which both elastic constants can be extracted.

4 NUMERICAL IMPLEMENTATION

The procedure for calculating the effective elastic constants κ and μ of the generated Delaunay network model involves the following two steps:

Step 1: *Generation of one realization (specimen) of the Voronoi and its dual Delaunay networks.*

Once a realization is created, the following operations are carried out:

i) Random assignment of the two phases (soft and hard) to all network's vertices according to a given volume fraction V_p without any special correlation.

ii) Subjecting the boundary of the network to a uniform in-plane tension corresponding to a macroscopic strain $\varepsilon_{11} = \varepsilon_{22}$, and then calculating the total energy $U_{(1)}$ set in the network as the sum of all energies in all its edges (bonds), which are modeled as linear springs.

iii) Subjecting the boundary of the network to a uniform extension in the x_1 direction and a uniform compression in the x_2 direction, corresponding to a simple shear in a coordinate system rotated by 45° ,

and then calculating the total energy $U_{(2)}$ as before. This assignment of boundary condition yields the shear modulus of the realization directly.

iv) Defining the energy of a 2D linear elastic continuum of area $=L^2$:

$$U = \frac{V}{2} [\kappa \varepsilon_{ij}^0 \varepsilon_{jj}^0 + 2\mu (\varepsilon_{ij}^0 \varepsilon_{ij}^0 - \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_{ii}^0 \varepsilon_{jj}^0)] \quad (10)$$

and equating the energy of the discrete model to that of continuum model allows calculating the bulk modulus to be:

$$\kappa = \frac{2U_{(1)}}{V(\varepsilon_{11} + \varepsilon_{22})^2} \quad (11)$$

Similarly, the shear modulus can be calculated as:

$$\mu = \frac{2U_{(2)}}{V(\varepsilon_{12})^2} \quad (12)$$

Next, considering the relationships between (κ, μ) and (E, ν) :

$$\kappa = \frac{E}{2(1-\nu)}, \quad \mu = \frac{E}{2(1+\nu)} \quad (13)$$

Where E is the Young's modulus and ν is the Poisson's ratio, the following relationship exists for a 2D plane:

$$\nu = \frac{\kappa - \mu}{\kappa + \mu} \quad (14)$$

Step 2: Carrying out steps i) through iv) using a Monte Carlo simulation for a sufficient number of realizations

The effective Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the medium are obtained as the ensemble averaging:

$$E^{eff} = \langle E \rangle = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n E_i}{n}, \quad \nu^{eff} = \langle \nu \rangle = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \nu_i}{n} \quad (15)$$

The above procedure of calculating E^{eff} and ν^{eff} is carried out by computer simulations, using two computer codes developed in Fortran90. One code generates the geometry of the Delany network and the second code carries out the mechanistic calculations by minimizing the energy of the discrete model using a conjugate gradient method [16]. This results in determining E^{eff} and ν^{eff} for each realization.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Effect of average grain size on the elastic moduli

The grain size is an important microstructure parameter for ceramics-based composites. This parameter can be obtained by fixing the dimension of the SPE to be $L = 1$ and defining the total number of grains m , from which it follows that $\delta = 1/d = \sqrt{m}$. For this study, we considered $\delta = 10, 20, 30, 40$ and 50 , implying that the total number of grains in the SPE is equal to $100, 400, 900, 1600$ and 2500 , respectively. Moreover, both, the particulates (primary phase) and the matrix (secondary phase) were assumed to be isotropic linear elastic for the simulation. Table 1 lists the Young's modulus and the Poisson's ratio for both original phases [13].

	E(GPa)	ν
Primary phase	800	0.1
Secondary phase	300	0.1

Table 1: Material properties.

The rule for assigning spring constants to all edges of the Delaunay networks is as follows:

Let each edge with length l be made of a link of the same cross section A and the same Young's modulus E , then the spring constant is $k^e = EA/l$. The EA values are the spring constants that yields an effective elastic moduli for a homogeneous medium, that is for all primary phase or for all secondary phase with $V_p = 1$ and $V_p = 0$, respectively.

Based on these parameters, a total of 500 realizations were simulated for each setup to ensure capturing the variability in the microstructure sufficiently. The simulation produces estimates the Young's modulus and the Poisson's ratio for each realization, which can then be statistically analyzed. The results presented here include a volume fraction of the primary phase of 0.2 and 0.5 .

The effective Young's modulus values at $V_p = 0.5$ are compared to results found in literature, based on the application of a variety of different methods. As shown in Table 2, the results obtained in this article are slightly larger than those in the literature. This is a direct consequence of the effect of essential boundary conditions used in this study. Periodic boundary conditions tendentially result in smaller values of moduli. This will be studied extensively in the next phase of this work.

Microstructure	E_{V-D} (GPa)	E_{Hom} (GPa)	E_{LD} (GPa)	E_{EMT} (GPa)	E_{HS} (GPa)
5x5, 10x10	505	465	478	463	460-481

Table 2: Effective Young's modulus of different methods.

Commencing with $V_p = 0.2$, Fig. 2 shows the dependency of the Young's modulus upon δ and highlights that the estimated average value (mean) is almost constant. Analyzing the variance of this material constant, however, a different picture emerges. The smaller the diameter of the secondary phase the less variability can be noted for the Young's modulus. This is not surprising and follows from the fact that as $\delta \rightarrow \infty$, the SPE becomes deterministic rather than stochastic and hence, the variability converges to zero.

Figure 2: Mean and 95% confidence region of Young's modulus versus δ ($V_p = 0.2$).

Next, Fig. 3 shows the same analysis for the Poisson's ratio. There is some minor variation in the estimated mean value of ν and the variance decreases significantly with the decrease in diameter of the second phase enclosures. This follows from the fact that the specimen, in a statistical sense, becomes more homogeneous as δ increases and results in less variability.

Figure 3: Mean and 95% confidence region of Poisson's ratio versus δ ($V_p = 0.2$).

Figs. 4 and 5 present the analysis of the Monte Carlo simulations for the larger volume fraction of the primary phase of 0.5. The estimated mean of Young's modulus is almost constant as function of δ as depicted in Fig. 4. While it increases as volume fraction increases (Fig. 5). This follows from the higher content of the harder phase that, according to Table 1, has a higher value for E .

Figure 4: Mean and 95%confidence region of Young's modulus versus δ ($V_p = 0.5$).

In contrast, comparing Figs. 3 and 5 yields that the higher volume fraction reduces the Poisson's ratio to an average value of 0.078 from 0.082 for $V_p = 0.2$. This results is consistent with results of granular material, as discussed in Ref [10] where authors conclude: *"This means that effective Poisson's ratio of a mixture of two phases is a convex function of the volume fraction, so that it may become negative when V_p and V_s are still both positive. This behavior of ν is a consequence of the dependencies of κ and μ on volume fraction (V_p) and contrast i.e. ratio of hard to soft. It is interesting to observe that effective Poisson's ratio is lower than ν either of pure phase at $V_p = 0$ or 1.0 ".*

This interesting behaviour may be attributed to the fact that Poisson's ratio is a measure of relative deformation of a specimen in two perpendicular directions which depends on two elastic constants rather than one as in the case of Young's modulus.

Figure 5: Mean and 95%confidence region of Poisson's ratio versus δ ($V_p = 0.2$).

5.2 Effect of primary phase volume content on the elastic moduli

This subsection investigates the effect of the volume fraction of the primary phase upon the effective elastic moduli. Fig. 6 presents the dependency of E upon V_p , indicating that there is an approximate parabolic relationship between the two

Variables. The resulting least squares estimate is $E = 180.8353V_p^2 + 318.3286V_p + 300.1402$. It is also interesting to note that the variances of the smaller or larger volume fractions, i.e. those closer to 0.0 or 1.0 are negligible, while those within the range $V_p = [0.2 \ 0.8]$ are significant.

Figure 6: Mean and 95% confidence region of Young's modulus versus V_p ($\delta = 40$).

This, however, is to be expected and follows from the fact that in this range the variability in local distribution of elastic moduli is highest where toward end of range of V_p , one phase is dominant which significantly reduces variability in the distribution of both phases. Finally, Fig. 7 depicts the resulting dependency of ν upon V_p . A good approximation of the convex relationship between the estimated mean value and volume fraction is given by the following regression equation $\nu = -0.0860 V_p^3 + 0.2160 V_p^2 - 0.1299 V_p + 0.0996$. The mean estimation decreases by up to 25% for $V_p = 0.4$. It should also be noted that, as for the Young's modulus, the variance in ν , driven by the randomness of the dispersity and shape distribution, is significant between $V_p = [0.2 \ 0.8]$.

In a similar fashion to the observations for the Young's modulus, if one phase is dominant the variability decreases. In contrast, if none of the phases is dominant, which is the case within the range $[0.2 \ 0.8]$, the variability increases resulting from the variation in dispersity and the shape distribution.

Figure 7: Mean and 95% confidence region of Poisson's ratio versus V_p ($\delta = 40$).

It is also important to note the observed concave dependency of ν upon V_p is not specific to the composite material studied in this article. Such concave relationships have also been reported for other composites, for example granular materials [10].

6 CONCLUSIONS

This article has developed a discrete random Delaunay network model to estimate the effective elastic moduli of ceramics-based composites along with its scatter. The developed model considers randomness in the distribution of phases and the grain size effect. Resulting from the geometric disorder of a Delaunay network, it is not possible to determine the effective, macroscopic moduli analytically, because the strain field under uniform-strain boundary conditions is non-uniform—which necessitates a computational model. The analysis of the Monte Carlo simulations yielded the following conclusions:

- The effective Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio are independent of the size of the SPE, as randomness is only considered for the physical properties and distribution of phases.
- The variability of both estimated effective elastic constants decreases as δ increases, where the microstructure becomes, asymptotically, deterministic.
- Within the range of volume fraction $V_p = 0.2 \dots 0.8$, the physical randomness in effective mechanical properties are more pronounced producing the highest scatter of values.
- A similar trend also emerged for the effective Poisson's ratio, which is a function of V_p .
- The effective Poisson's ratio is highly affected by the volume fraction of the primary phase with a minimum estimated mean value of 0.078 for $V_p = 0.4$.

As the present modeling has been successfully applied to ceramics-based composite with randomness in the physical properties, future work will extend to study the randomness in the shape of grains and other microstructure parameters under periodic geometry and boundary conditions. Furthermore, including voids which is a more accurate representative of real material will be considered in future.

REFERENCES

- [1] M.P. D'Evelyn and T. Taniguchi, Elastic properties of translucent polycrystalline cubic boron nitride as characterized by the dynamic resonance method, *Diamond and related Materials*, **46**, 1999, pp. 1522-1526.
- [2] M. Guazzato and M. Albakrya, Strength, fracture toughness and microstructure of a selection of all-ceramic materials. Part II. Zirconia-based dental ceramics, *Dental Materials*, **20**, 2004, pp. 449-456.
- [3] D. Carolan, P. Alveen, A. Ivankovic and N. Murphy, N., Effect of notch root radius on fracture toughness of polycrystalline cubic boron nitride, *Eng. Fracture Mechanics*, **78**, 2011, pp. 2885-2895.
- [4] D. Carolan, A. Ivankovic and N. Murphy, Thermal shock resistance of polycrystalline cubic boron nitride, *J. of European Ceramics Society*, **32**, 2012, pp. 2581-2586.
- [5] X.Y. Teng, H.I. Liu and C.Z. Huang, Effect of Al_2O_3 particle size on the mechanical properties of alumina-based ceramics, *Materials Science and Engineering*, **A452**, 2007, pp. 545-551.
- [6] K.F. Cai, D.S. McLachlan, N. Axen and R. Manyasab, Preparation, microstructures and properties of Al_2O_3 -TiC composites, *Ceramics International*, **28**, 2002, pp. 217-222.
- [7] N. Liu, M. Shi and Y.D. Xu, Effect of starting powders size on the Al_2O_3 -TiC composites, *Int. J. of Refractory Metal and Hard Materials*, **22**, 2004, pp. 265-269.
- [8] E. Aslan, N. Camuscu and B. Birgoen, Design optimization of cutting parameters when turning hardened AISI 4140 steel (63 HRC) with $Al_2O_3 + TiCN$ mixed ceramic tool, *Materials & Design*, **28**, 2007, pp. 1618-1622.

- [9] M. Ostoja-Starzewski and C. Wang, Linear elasticity of planar Delaunay networks: random field characterization of effective moduli, *Acta Mechanica*, **80**, 1989, pp. 61-80.
- [10] K. Alzebdeh and M. Ostoja-Starzewski, On a spring-network model and effective elastic moduli of granular materials, *ASME J. of Applied Mechanics*, **66**, 1999, pp. 172 – 180.
- [11] M. Nygard and P. Gudmundson, Three-dimensional periodic Voronoi grain models and micromechanical FE simulations of a two-phase steel, *Computational Materials Science*, **24**, 2002, pp. 513–519.
- [12] T.T. Zhou, C.Z. Huang, H.I. Liu, J. Wang, B. Zou and H.T. Zhu, Molecular dynamics simulation of Al₂O₃-SiC interface, *Computational Materials Science*, **54**, 2012, pp. 150-156.
- [13] P. Alveen, D. Carolan, D. McNamara, N. Murphy and A. Ivankovic, Micromechanical modeling of ceramic based composites with statically representative synthetic microstructures, *Computational Materials Science*, **79**, 2013, pp. 960-970.
- [14] W. Dong, J. Zhao, J.I. Zhao, L. Anhai and X. Chen, Microstructure-level modeling and simulation of the flexure behaviour of ceramics tool materials, *Computational Materials Science*, **83**, 2014, pp. 434-442.
- [15] K. Alzebdeh and M. Ostoja-Starzewski, Micromechanically based stochastic finite elements, *Finite Elements in Analysis and Design*, **15**, 1993, pp. 35-41.
- [16] M. Ostoja-Starzewski, K. Alzebdeh and I. Jasiuk, Linear elasticity of planar networks.III: self-consistent approximations, *Acta Mechanica*, **110**, 1995, pp. 57-72.